

Grappling with Methodology: Key Considerations

Stephanie O'Connor

Email: stephanie.oconnor247@mail.dcu.ie

Abstract

Grappling with methodology is a process that all researchers must go through, but it can be a daunting task for the novice researcher. This article outlines the methodological approach that this research will use, reflecting on the philosophical assumptions of a social constructivist worldview; the benefits and challenges of qualitative inquiry; the role as a researcher held in tension with the role as a teacher; and the decision to adopt a case study approach. A constant consideration throughout this process is the importance of ethical conduct, and the ethical implications for this project will be discussed.

Key words

Methodology, grounded theory, well-being, education, Catholic schools, transformative paradigm, qualitative research

Introduction

The aim of this research is to develop a theory of well-being underpinned by Catholic theology that will go towards the development of a well-being framework that can be integrated into Catholic schools. This article will justify the use of qualitative data and provide a rationale for holding the philosophical assumptions of the social constructivist worldview. Creswell & Poth (2018, pp.21-22) identify the importance for qualitative researchers of an awareness of and active reporting on their own philosophical assumptions. Therefore, an engagement of the researcher's own assumptions and the implications for this research will be explored. This article will reflect upon the choice to adopt a case study approach to the research, including some of the challenges faced when embarking upon this methodology. The ethical implications will also be discussed, highlighting some of the steps taken to ensure that the project meets the ethical standards expected in research (Flick, 2020, p.40).

Selecting a Research Approach

Every researcher brings their own philosophical assumptions and beliefs to any piece of research (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p.15). Creswell & Poth (*ibid.*) also argue that identifying these beliefs and determining whether they should be actively present in the research is the challenge faced by any researcher (*ibid.*). Ontological, epistemological and axiological assumptions lend direction to the study and are applied through the use of research paradigms (*ibid.*, pp.20-21). Huff (2009, p.16) highlights the importance of philosophy in research, identifying the key areas that are likely to be influenced by the researcher. These include research aims and the context of our scholarly community among others. Due to the inherent

influence that our own beliefs have on our research, it is necessary for the researcher to have a clear understanding of her own philosophical assumptions, research design and research methods (data collection, data analysis and interpretation) (Creswell & Creswell, 2018, pp.3-4). Key assumptions made by the researcher in this project were acknowledged and will be more widely addressed later in this article when considering the role of the researcher. This was particularly relevant due to the researcher's current role in education and her investment in student well-being.

Embedded within educational research is a range of assumptions and paradigms, each indicating a particular world view of the researcher. The postpositive worldview is more often held by quantitative researchers (*ibid.*, p.6) which challenges the traditional concept of the infallibility of knowledge (Phillips & Burbules, 2000, p.29). Social constructivism is an approach more typically held by qualitative researchers who aim to identify the complexity of views from their participants; views that have been constructed from their social and cultural experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2018, p.8). A pragmatic approach takes many forms but there is a focus on the outcomes of the research that provide a solution to a particular problem (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p.27).

The worldview that underpins this research is predominantly the social constructivist framework, but the transformative framework is also drawn upon. Social constructivism seeks to gain understanding of the subjective experiences of individuals, developing meanings of their experiences (*ibid.*, p.24). Due to the variety of these meanings, the researcher aims to explore the complexities, moving away from a narrower lens. Knowledge is therefore developed through an understanding of the participants' views of the situation. In this research, policy documents will be examined, alongside interviews with staff that will provide context of the practical application of these policies. It is then the experiences of both the staff and students that will provide the basis of the knowledge; identifying their views of the current well-being provision in the school. The constructivist researcher recognises that their own background will shape their interpretation (*ibid.*), therefore, this will be considered when analysing the data, which is the next stage in this project.

However, this research also aims to give a voice to students on the issue of their well-being as this remains an area of which there is a limited amount of research available. Therefore, the transformative framework is also drawn upon as a worldview that guides this project. Creswell & Poth (*ibid.*, p.25) outline the basic tenet of this worldview - that knowledge is not neutral and the purpose of gaining knowledge should be for the betterment of society. Mertens (2015, pp.86-87) believes that those who may benefit from a transformative worldview include those who are marginalised and her theoretical perspectives include positive psychology and resilience theory (Sweetman *et al.*, 2010, p.442). Therefore, the research should contain 'an action agenda for reform that may change the lives of participants, [and] the institutions in which they live and work...' (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p.25). One aim of transformative research is to provide a voice for the participants, allowing their views to be heard, thus advancing a change for their benefit (*ibid.*). In this research, the

action agenda is to create a well-being framework that will enhance the lives of students, not just during their school career, but for life. So often, school policy is developed without the consideration of students' views and for Shotton and Burton (2018, p.3), the move to a knowledge-based curriculum in the UK, with a purely academic focus, has left many young people feeling that school simply does not cater to their needs. Therefore, this research is intertwined with politics, confronting the perceived lack of practical application of well-being provision, despite organisations at both government and church level advocating its importance. It was deemed important to not only collect data from school policy and policy makers, e.g. school management and pastoral leads, but to include the viewpoints of the students. Kosher & Ben-Arieh (2017, p.63) highlight that research into adult well-being has traditionally been prioritised over research into children's well-being. Furthermore, the research that has been done on children's well-being has tended to focus on objective descriptions, such as their reality as perceived by adults, rather than the subjective evaluations of the young person. This research attempts to avoid this potential limitation, which further allows for a critical analysis of the systems in place and how effective they are perceived by those who the systems are there to serve. By doing this, the intention is to advocate for reform of the well-being structures in Catholic schools. Advocating for such social reform is yet another strand of a transformative worldview.

Philosophical Assumptions

The four philosophical assumptions are beliefs about ontology, epistemology, axiology and methodology (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p.19; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018, p.19). These will influence the nature of the research and the lens through which the data is collected and analysed. As previously noted, all researchers, consciously or otherwise, bring certain beliefs, world views and value sets to their work (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p.15). The impact these have on any given research project are far reaching, from the core question itself through to how the data is collected and analysed. These assumptions are developed through our life experiences and can also be seen in decisions we make, such as where we choose to study - in this case, Dublin City University - or who we choose to study with - our choice of supervisors or colleagues. These philosophical assumptions will influence the theories that guide research, which are often made apparent in qualitative studies (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p.15). Creswell & Poth (*ibid.*) not only encourage an awareness of these assumptions and beliefs, but an active acknowledgment of them in the writing of the research.

Ontology relates to the nature of reality and ontological researchers embrace the fact that there are multiple realities or perspectives stemming from different sources of data (*ibid.*, p.20). This was taken into consideration in this research project, and a decision was therefore made to draw upon school policy documents alongside interviews to provide a range of perspectives. Blaikie (2000, p.8) asserts that 'ontological assumptions are concerned with what we believe constitutes social reality'. It is therefore unsurprising that research traditions that have emerged from different cultures and disciplines have differing assumptions that

underpin their approach to social inquiry (Grix, 2001, p.27). These variety of assumptions become evident in qualitative research, when researchers aim to report on these multiple realities and perspectives by gathering data from a variety of sources (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p.20). The ontology that underpins this research is the assumption that knowledge is constructed through uncovering the lived reality of the participants. Therefore, it is expected that different themes will emerge in the findings as the different perspectives are analysed.

Ontology is heavily intertwined with epistemology; the latter is concerned with the theory of knowledge and how we come to gain that knowledge (Grix, 2001, p.27). Epistemology is a constantly evolving phenomenon, focusing on the gathering of knowledge, its acquisition, and developing what is already known (*ibid.*). Walsh *et. al.* (2015, p.587) argued that clarity of one's epistemology leads to 'well-defined and epistemologically congruent research outcomes'. In terms of a qualitative study, knowledge is discovered through the subjective realities of the participants, which also accounts for why many qualitative researchers choose to conduct their study in the field; context provides deeper understanding of what is being said (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p.21). Therefore, this research gathered data through semi-structured interviews, with individual schools purposefully chosen to represent a range of educational contexts. This will be discussed in more detail later in the article. To gain knowledge, a researcher must get as close to that knowledge as possible, removing as many objective barriers as they can (Guba & Lincoln, 1988, p.94).

An axiological assumption focuses on the question of values, acknowledging that all researchers bring their own values to a study but in a qualitative project, those values are made known (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p.21). Therefore, the axiological assumptions in this research will be made clear later in the article.

Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods

Rather than being understood as distinct and separate, Creswell & Creswell (2018, p.3) believe that qualitative and quantitative methods are different ends of the same spectrum rather than distinct and polar categories. Mixed methods research is in the centre of the spectrum, incorporating elements of both (*ibid.*).

Creswell & Poth (*ibid.*, p.7) note that attempting to define qualitative research is a challenging task, articulating instead the concern of coining a fixed definition. Emphasising this difficulty, Denzin and Lincoln (2018, p.xv) convey the fluidity of defining 'qualitative' research, stating that 'the open-ended nature of the qualitative research project leads to a perpetual resistance against attempts to impose a single, umbrella-like paradigm over the entire project'. In attempting to draw something of a definition for qualitative research, they admit the complexities of such a task, but qualify the definition, asserting that qualitative research is 'a set of complex interpretive practises...[that] embraces tensions and contradictions, including disputes over its methods and the forms its findings and interpretations take', (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018, p.13).

This research will use a qualitative methodological approach due to its potential to provide a deeper understanding of the research question, which in turn will feed into the development of a well-being framework. A quantitative approach was considered, which would have provided a wider participant base. However, in-depth interviews will provide the profundity of information required. This will provide a greater insight into the experiences of both staff and students in Catholic schools and their response to the well-being provision. The challenges and pitfalls of a qualitative approach were scrutinised. Spencer *et al.* (2014, p.81) identify the ongoing tension between qualitative and quantitative approaches, arguing that the criticisms of qualitative inquiry are often framed in contrast to the more widely accepted quantitative approach. Denzin and Lincoln (2018, p.8) state that, ‘politicians and hard scientists refer to qualitative researchers as *journalists* or “soft” scientists. Their work is termed unscientific, only exploratory, or subjective.’ However, the subjective nature of this research is not deemed as a negative. Rather, it is arguably the most reliable method of investigating people’s response to well-being provision, which is an entirely subjective experience. Qualitative researchers are also declared guilty of researcher bias that is rejected by experimental scientists (Carey, 1989, p.99). Carey (*ibid.*) also adds that the value-laden researcher is also looked down upon by scientists who defend a value-free position. However, it could be argued that a ‘value-free’ researcher simply does not exist. As identified by Creswell & Poth (2018, p.15), every researcher brings their own underlying beliefs and assumptions to any piece of research, be that qualitative or quantitative. However, further criticism is directed towards the truth statements made by the qualitative researcher; statements that cannot be verified, according to critics (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018, p.8). For some, the only legitimacy of qualitative research is to reinforce the more valid quantitative methods (*ibid.*). Whilst not denying the values of quantitative research, this still allows qualitative data to be legitimised by numerical facts and figures.

A mixed methods approach was considered for this research as it adopts aspects of both quantitative and qualitative methodologies and amalgamates them to gain a richness of data that provides additional insight into a particular research question (Creswell & Creswell, 2018, p.14). Mixed methods research allows the researcher to juxtapose a variety of perspectives to gather data that is stronger than if simply quantitative or qualitative methods were used (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p.8). However, to use mixed methods research effectively, Tashakkori and Teddlie (2012, p.777) argue that the researcher must be suitably skilled in both methodologies. A mixed methods approach was ultimately rejected based on the desire to explore the lived experience of students regarding the well-being provision in their respective Catholic schools. There is currently limited research on the area of an applied understanding of a specifically Catholic theology of well-being. However, this research aims to construct more knowledge in this field which will lead to further research projects that could aim to have a more quantitative approach.

Creswell & Poth (2018, p.43) ultimately favour the qualitative approach, valuing the researcher as a key instrument in the research process, emphasising how their background and experiences inform the research and its interpretation. Equally, the importance of detail

gathered from talking to individuals and groups about their personal experiences of a particular issue provides far richer data than can be provided by numerical capturing (*ibid.*, p.45). Conveying stories, contexts and a deeper understanding of an issue are all strengths of qualitative inquiry over that of quantitative (*ibid.*). For this research, statistics would provide less of an insight into people's experience of well-being structures in a school setting than interviews, which allow for far greater profundity. A quantitative approach to research focuses on the collection, analysis and interpretation of data that is quantifiable and mathematically verifiable (Creswell & Creswell, 2018, p.4). Collecting numerical data allows a generalisation of a particular issue across a group of people (Babbie, 2015, p.415). In doing so, objective theories, devised prior to the collection of data, can be tested, examining the relationship between different variables (Flick, 2020, p.10). A considerable strength of quantitative research is the breadth of data that can be collected from a wide range of subjects, as well as a perceived lack of researcher bias (Brown & McNamara, 2020). However, the limitations of pre-set answers and a lack of contextual information from the participant may result in the data being unable to give any significant depth to a particular problem (*ibid.*). Due to the subjective nature of research into well-being provision, it was deemed that merely quantitative data would not provide the depth of inquiry needed to provide a deep understanding of the phenomenon. The research had to be primarily based in a qualitative methodology.

Role and Values of the Researcher

As previously mentioned, the value-laden nature of a qualitative research project is bound up in biases and values of the researcher. In this study, the role of the researcher is that of an outsider - not formerly known to the schools in which the research will be conducted. Fay (1996 p.20) believed that being an outsider provided the researcher with the required distance from the subject to fully know it. Not being entrenched in the intricacies of a membership allows an outsider researcher to bring a fresh perspective and appreciate the wider intricacies of a system.

However, as a teacher in a Catholic school, the context is not completely unknown to the researcher, so is therefore part of the membership of the group being studied. Insider researcher is defined by research conducted in a setting to which the researcher belongs and therefore shares an experiential base with the group being studied (Dwyer & Buckle, 2009, p.58). Membership status may provide a sense of legitimacy, encouraging participants to be more open, thereby enhancing the richness of the data (*ibid.*). Drever (1995, p.31) argues that people's engagement in the research will be influenced by their own preconceptions about the researcher. Mercer (2007, p.7) terms this, 'informant bias'. However, membership status may also present challenges if the researcher is unable to fully detach themselves from the participants or the data gathered (Dwyer & Buckle, 2009, p.58) or project their own internal values onto the participants (*ibid.*).

An alternative understanding is presented by McDermid *et al.* (2014, p.61) who suggest that a researcher is on a continuum - balanced between an objective outsider and a subjective observer. They propose that because we are influenced by our position as a researcher, we can never completely occupy the position of insider or outsider; rather, the researcher can only truly occupy the 'space in between' (*ibid.*). Dwyer and Buckle (2009, p.58) suggest that whilst the researcher may be part of the culture being studied, there may be subcultures that she is unaware of. They advise that assuming no knowledge of a situation ensures that the researcher remains fully aware rather than relying on presuppositions (*ibid.*).

The concept of a continuum was a helpful one. At the time of the research, the researcher was not working in any of the schools involved in the project. A conscious decision was made to exclude the Catholic Secondary (post-primary) school in which the researcher was working, from the study. Concerns about formerly established relationships with participants and the potential for researcher bias meant that it would not have been appropriate. However, having worked in Catholic schools, the researcher was familiar with some of the ways in which a Catholic ethos can be embraced by a school community. Similarly, a considerable interest in the question of student well-being provided the researcher with a greater understanding of the issue. This, alongside the understanding of wider literature on the subject is termed by Simons (2009, p.32) as 'foreshadowed issues'. It allows the values of the researcher to be known but acknowledges that previous assumptions may be changed considering the data gathered.

It is also necessary to acknowledge the roles within schools that the researcher has held, that have had a specific well-being focus. Having worked with both staff and students from a variety of schools on their well-being and a dedicated interest in the development of well-being provision within an educational setting further highlights the underlying beliefs and assumptions held by the researcher. The researcher's teaching roles have been entirely UK based, and there has been no first-hand experience of Irish schools. This does not mean that there is a bias towards the UK schooling system, but it is important to be aware of this element of the researcher's background. The aim is to present the benefits and challenges experienced in both settings, to develop a framework from which Catholic schools in both Ireland and England will profit.

Case Study Approach

Creswell & Poth (2007, pp.11-12) identify five main approaches to qualitative research: case study, ethnography, phenomenology, narrative and grounded theory. Whilst grounded theory was considered as a possible methodology, it was ultimately rejected on the grounds that an in depth review of the literature was deemed a necessity prior to data collection; a concept that is widely rejected amongst traditional grounded theory proponents.

Instead, a case study methodology was adopted. Hamilton and Corbett-Whittier (2013, p.4) assert that case study research in education has gained traction since the 1970s as a reaction

to the dominant positivist model; an approach that applied greater emphasis to the statistical measurement of data as a means of obtaining valid and rational insights into education. Now, the case study is a popular method of research design adopted across a range of research fields. Bassey (1999, pp.22-27) highlights the various definitions that have been applied to the term 'case study'. Merriam (1998, p.27) proposes that the challenge of trying to identify the definition of 'case study' stems from the fact that the unit of study (the case) and the process of investigation are often conflated, thus causing some confusion. Over time, Merriam adapted her initial understanding of the case study (defined in terms of its end product) to reflect more closely the thinking of Smith (1978) and Stake (1995), stating that the most important aspect of a case study is determining that it is a bounded unit (Hamilton and Corbett-Whittier, 2013, p.7). Merriam (1998, p.27) writes that the case, 'is a thing, a single entity, a unit around which there are boundaries. I can "fence in" what I am going to study'. If the phenomenon being studied does not have intrinsic boundaries, within which it operates and can be observed, it cannot be defined as a case (Merriam, 1998, p.28). Similarly, Stake (1995, p.2) argues that 'a case is a specific, a complex, functioning thing'. Stake (1995, p.2) differentiates between something specific, for example, a child, a program within a school, or a group of schools - all of which may be defined as a case, from that which is more abstract; the relationship between schools, or the policies of school reform. The latter are less likely to be considered a case. Pertinent to this research is the definition offered by Yin (1984, p.23) who states that a case study is, 'an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context; when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident, and in which multiple sources of evidence are used'. Gillham (2010, p.2) also notes that using multiple sources of evidence is a key characteristic of case study research. In this research, policy documents will be drawn upon, in tandem with the data collected from staff and students within the school.

A collective case study has been chosen for this research for several reasons. Stake (1995, p.5) proposes that a collective case study 'may be designed with more concern for representation', despite the sample still being relatively small. A collective case study is the chosen methodology for this research because it is a bounded study of a small group of schools from within the Dublin and Birmingham archdioceses. It seeks to offer insight into the lived experience of well-being provision in Catholic schools, offering a comprehensive comparison between this provision in Dublin and Birmingham. Schools were selected to increase the reliability of findings, the challenges of which will be examined later in this article.

Data collection will be through semi-structured interviews, conducted online via Zoom, due to the COVID-19 pandemic. These interviews will be analysed alongside individual school policy on well-being to provide a holistic picture of how each school approaches well-being provision for students and the lived experience of this. Yin (2009, p.36) identifies three forms of case study: exploratory, descriptive and explanatory. This research adopts an explanatory

approach, attempting not only to explore the phenomenon but to provide an explanation as to how and why a school may or may not have a successful approach to well-being provision.

All research methods will present both benefits and limitations. A significant criticism of the case study approach is a perceived lack of generalisability. Schofield (2011, p.70) argues that many qualitative researchers actively reject generalisability as a goal, citing Denzin (1983, pp.133-134) who stated that:

‘The interpretivist rejects the generalisation as a goal and never aims to draw randomly selected samples of human experiences. For the interpretivist, every instance of social interaction, if thickly described (Geertz, 1973), represents a slice from the life world that is the proper subject matter for interpretive inquiry.’

Stake (1995, p.7) acknowledges that case study ‘seems a poor basis for generalisation’ as only a single, or small number of cases will be studied. However, Stake (*ibid.*) clarifies that the case/s will be studied at length and in depth, which will inevitably result in particular aspects repeatedly occurring in the data. As such, certain generalisations can be drawn. However, Labaree (2004, p.17) asserts that the knowledge gained by educational researchers is ‘the softest of the soft fields’, which prevents them from making any strong claims about their findings. Despite this, Gomm *et al.* (2011, p.98) argue that denying the possibility of case studies providing the basis of empirical generalisability is to unnecessarily concede to critics. Whilst the generalisability of case study research may be in question, this research proposes that the findings will be relatable to other Catholic schools in both Ireland and the UK. The context of each school and the participants have been purposefully selected to further increase the relatability of the findings.

It is not the aim of this research to simply provide a description of a single event, but to draw upon a particular phenomenon experienced in multiple contexts in order to create a framework that is widely relevant to the context of Catholic schools. Therefore, a single event is not examined because of its intrinsic interest, and nor does this research assume that the case is a microcosm of a larger system. Instead, a multi-site case study approach has been adopted which Schofield (2011, p.79) argues increases the generalisability of a project. She states that the findings that emerge from the study of several heterogeneous sites are more likely to be robust, allowing generalisations to be made to a variety of other sites (*ibid.*). A comparative strategy is also undertaken in this research, which further increases generalisability (*ibid.*). VanWynsberghe and Khan (2007, p.85) propose that by comparing a case to prior knowledge, another case, experience or theory, one enhances its generalisability. However, Schofield (2011, p.80) acknowledges that smaller numbers of sites, whilst allowing for a greater range of data without risking anything of the depth and breadth of description, still face the threat of a lack of generalisability. Nonetheless, an advantage of case studies are the rich, thick descriptions that are borne of studying a specific context. In this case, the interviews will capture the lived experience of both teachers and students regarding the well-being provision in a range of schools in both Dublin and Birmingham archdioceses. This research does not aim to evaluate the efficacy of this in every school, but rather to address the

gap highlighted in the literature between a Catholic theology of well-being and the practical application in schools.

Research Participants

For this research, the sampling was purposeful, based on several criteria. Initially, the schools had to be chosen that would form the basis of the research. In the UK, only schools who were deemed 'Good' or 'Outstanding' by the Diocese in their most recent Section 48 inspection were selected. These inspections evaluate the Catholic life of the school, collective worship and all areas of Religious Education. Schools deemed below 'Good' were consciously rejected, because this research is aiming to examine if and how effectively Catholic school policy impacts student well-being. Therefore, the school must have Catholic values at the forefront of its mission.

Similarly, the student demographic was also considered in order to include students from all backgrounds. In Ireland, a DEIS (Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Ireland) school was selected from a more disadvantaged area of Dublin and a single sex school consisting of students from a more privileged socio-economic background. In the UK, a single sex school deemed a 'World Class School' was chosen, alongside a school from a disadvantaged area.

Participants were also purposefully chosen. As the aim of this research is to gain an understanding of how a school aimed to provide well-being structures to its students and how this was received, it was decided to interview both staff and students. Three staff members were selected based on their role in the school; one member from the management team, one involved in pastoral care and one classroom teacher. Sometimes, these roles overlapped, for example, a member of management may also be responsible for pastoral care and be a classroom teacher. In terms of students, three from each school were selected across the year groups: one who had regular access to the well-being provision, one who was involved in the implementation or development of well-being structures, e.g. student council, and one who had never sought or been provided with extra pastoral support. It was important to distinguish between the well-being provision that was provided to all students and the additional structures in place specifically for those who required it. As a result, the number of participants to take part in this research was thirty-six.

Semi-structured Interviews

Berg and Lune (2014, p.115) propose that interviews are an effective means of understanding the perceptions of participants regarding a particular phenomenon. Similarly, Denscombe (2017, p.202) states that interviews are best utilised when the interviewer wants to explore complex and subtle phenomena, such as opinions, emotions, experiences and complex issues that call for a detailed understanding of how things work or are interconnected.

Semi-structured interviews, whilst maintaining a systematic interview schedule, allow the interviewer the flexibility to digress from the pre-planned questions. Berg and Lune (2014, p.112) state that this is not just allowed, but it is expected that the interviewer will probe

beyond the prepared questions. This flexibility was important for this research, particularly when interviewing students, as they often required further questioning to provide more detail in their answers. This ensured that the data collected was not superficial but identified and probed the emerging themes. Robson (2002, p.270) states that additional questions can be included during semi-structured interviews, but equally, questions can be omitted or wording can be changed to provide greater clarity to the participants. For this project, the flexible style of questioning allowed participants to reflect on their answers and critically evaluate their experiences. This method of questioning allows for much deeper and richer data than would be gained through a qualitative method such as questionnaires. This is further supported by Bell (1999, p.135) who states that:

A skilful interviewer can follow up ideas, probe responses and investigate motives and feelings, which the questionnaire can never do. The way in which a response is made (tone of voice, facial expression, hesitation etc.) can provide information that a written response would conceal (1999, p.135).

Ethics and the Impact of COVID-19

Initially, the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of Dublin City University granted ethical approval for face-to-face focus group interviews, conducted in ten schools; five in the Archdiocese of Birmingham and five in the Archdiocese of Dublin. However, in light of restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic, considerable changes were made to the methodology. Students from a range of year groups were to form the focus groups. However, school restrictions limited students from mixing with others outside of their class or year group 'bubble'. Therefore, the decision was made to move to individual interviews. The benefit of this was that students would not experience any peer pressure and all those interviewed would have an equal opportunity to fully voice their opinions. However, this did mean that the number of participants had to be curtailed. The final decision was made to interview three students in six schools, which was also based on the ongoing strain that schools are under whilst trying to function amidst a pandemic. Whilst still providing a breadth of participants, this would also keep the interview time and amount of data to analyse manageable. The number of staff participating was, and remained at, three per school.

However, this change meant an amendment application was to be made to the REC as the research had to move entirely online. Online research also required extra documentation, for example, a Zoom protocol for staff, students and parents. Once this was prepared, the amendment application was sent to the REC and received approval.

The ethical considerations for this study focused primarily on the safeguarding of the young people involved, and the anonymity and right to privacy of all participants. Data collection remained in line with the British Educational Research Association Guidelines (2018), maintaining the highest level of data protection protocols and ethical conduct. Creswell & Creswell (2018, p.88) identify the need to anticipate any ethical issues that may arise during

the research process. Therefore, the vulnerabilities of the participants were considered, and all precautions were taken to ensure the safety and well-being of all those involved. For example, whilst the interview questions did not focus on specific cases of well-being provision, there remained the possibility that some may have found the topic sensitive. Therefore, a pastoral member of staff was available to all student participants before, during and after the interview in case they become upset. Similarly, to ensure complete privacy, the participants will not be named in the results of the study and any details in the transcript that could identify them or the school will be anonymised.

Research Procedures

Following the ethical approval from Dublin City University, the schools were contacted to explain the research project. Authorisation and permission from the school Principals were granted before any interviews were arranged and conducted. Challenges were faced when several schools originally identified later dropped out of the research - some with no explanation provided. Equally, schools, particularly within the UK, were suffering the impact of high COVID cases amongst both staff and students, so several interviews had to be rearranged due to absence and isolation.

The liaison person for each school was sent the Plain Language Statements for students, parents and staff, as well as the Zoom protocol. Consent forms were obtained prior to the interviews being conducted.

With permission from each of the interviewees, the interviews were audio recorded. The quality was tested prior to each interview as a clear recording was important to capture both what the participant was saying and how it was being said. A reflective journal was kept by the researcher to make notes both during and after the interview. These will become a significant part of the data analysis procedure.

Conclusion

This article has provided a clear explanation of the research design of this study, the paradigm within which this research sits and a justification for adopting a qualitative approach. The limitations and advantages of these decisions have been analysed and it is worth reiterating that whilst the generalisability of the findings may be critiqued, the relatability to other Catholic schools is justifiable.

Drawing predominantly upon a social constructivist worldview, the construction of knowledge through the subjective views of the participants is assumed. However, the overall aims of this project also lend itself to strands of a transformative framework. Denzin (1998, p.338) states, 'Clearly simplistic classifications do not work. Any given qualitative researcher-as-bricoleur can be more than one thing at the same time, can be fitted into both

the tender- and the tough-minded categories'. As Corbin (2008, p.9) reflects on her own methodological stance that she is 'a mixture of many things', there are similar overlaps in this research. Constructing the concepts and theories of the participants into knowledge of well-being procedures in Catholic schools will allow the emerging data to form a practical framework of well-being, underpinned by Catholic theology.

References

- Babbie, E. (2015) *The Practice of Social Research*. 14th edn. Belmont: Wadsworth Publishing.
- Berg, B. & Lune, H. (2012) *Qualitative Research Methods for the Social Sciences*. 8th edn. New Jersey: Pearson.
- Blaikie, N. (2000) *Designing Social Research*. Cambridge: Polity.
- British Educational Research Association (2011) *Guidelines for Educational Research*. London: BERA.
- Brown, M. & McNamara, G. (2020) 'Graduate Training Elements: Mixed Methods Research', IE601: Mixed Methods Approach to Educational Research. Available at: loop.dcu.ie (Accessed: 21 October 2020).
- Bryant, A. & Charmaz, K. (2007) 'Introduction: Grounded Theory Research: Methods and Practices', in A. Bryant & K. Charmaz (eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Grounded Theory*. London: SAGE Publications, pp.1-26.
- Carey, J.W. (1989) *Culture as Communication*. Boston: Unwin Hyman.
- Charmaz, K. (2008) 'Constructionism and grounded theory', in J. A. Holstein & J. F. Gubrium (eds.). *Handbook of Constructionist Research*. New York: Guilford, pp.397-412.
- Charmaz, K. (2014). *Constructing grounded theory*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage.
- Corbin, J. & Strauss, A. (2008) 'Introduction', in J. Corbin & A. Strauss (eds.). *Basics of Qualitative Research: Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory*. London: SAGE Publications, pp.1-17.
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. (2011) *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. 2nd edn. London: SAGE Publications.
- Creswell, J. W. & Poth, C. N. (2018) *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design*. 4th edn. London: SAGE Publications.
- Denscombe, M. (2017) *The Good Research Guide: For small-scale social research projects*. 6th edn. London: Open University Press.
- Denzin, N.K. (1983) 'Interpretive interactionism', in G.Morgan (ed.), *Beyond Method: Strategies for Social Research*. Beverly Hills, CA: SAGE Publications, pp.129-146.
- Denzin, N. K. (1998) 'The art and politics of interpretation', in Denzin, N. K. & Lincoln, Y. (eds.) *Handbook of Qualitative Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, pp.500-515.

Denzin, N. & Lincoln, Y. (2018) 'Introduction: The Discipline and Practice of Qualitative Research', in N. Denzin & Y. Lincoln (eds.). *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research*. 5th edn. London: SAGE Publications, pp.1-26.

Drever, E. (1995) *Using semi-structured interviews in small-scale research*. Edinburgh: The Scottish Council for Research in Education.

Dwyer, S.C., & Buckle, J.L. (2009) 'The Space Between: On Being an Insider-Outsider in Qualitative Research', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 8 (1), pp.54-63.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/160940690900800105>

Fay, B. (1996). *Contemporary philosophy of social science: A multicultural approach*. Cambridge, UK: Blackwell.

Flick, U. (2019) *Doing Grounded Theory*. 2nd edn. London: SAGE Publications.

Garratt, D. (2018) 'Reflections on Being an Expert', *Grounded Theory Review*, 17 (1), pp.86-89. Available at: <http://groundedtheoryreview.com/>. (Accessed: 22 April 2021).

Geertz, C.(1973) 'Thick description: toward an interpretive theory of culture', in C.Geertz (ed.), *The Interpretation of Cultures*. New York: Basic Books, pp.310-323.

Gillham, B. (2010) *Case Study Research Methods*. London: Continuum.

Glaser, B. (1978). *Theoretical sensitivity: Advances in the methodology of grounded theory*. Mill Valley, CA: Sociology Press.

Glaser, B.G. (2018) 'Getting Started', *The Grounded Theory Review*, 17 (1), pp.3-6. Available at: <http://groundedtheoryreview.com/>. (Accessed: 22 April 2021).

Glaser, B.G. and Strauss, A.L. (1967) *The Discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies for Qualitative Research*. Chicago: Aldine.

Gomm, R., Hammersley, M., & Foster, P. (2009) 'Case Study and Generalisation' in R. Gomm, M. Hammersley & P. Foster (Eds.), *Case study method*. London: SAGE Publications, pp.98-115. <https://www-doi-org.dcu.idm.oclc.org/10.4135/9780857024367>

Grix, J. (2001) *Demystifying Postgraduate Research*. London: Bloomsbury Publishing.

Guba, E.G. & Lincoln, Y.S. (1988) 'Do inquiry paradigms imply inquiry methodologies?' in Fetterman, D.M. (ed.) *Qualitative approaches to evaluation in education*. New York: Praeger, pp.89-115.

Hamilton, L. & Corbett-Whittier, C. (2013) *Using Case Study in Educational Research*. London: SAGE Publications.

Holton, J., & Walsh, I. (2017) *Classic Grounded Theory: Applications With Qualitative and Quantitative Data*. London: SAGE Publications.

- Huff, A.S. (2009) *Designing Research for Publication*. London: SAGE Publications.
- Kosher, H. & Ben-Arieh, A. (2017) Religion and subjective well-being among children: A comparison of six religion groups, *Children and Youth Services Review*, (80), pp.63-7
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chidyouth.2017.06.049>.
- Labaree, D. (2010) 'The Lure of Statistics for Educational Researchers', in P. Smeyers & M. Depaepe (eds.). *Education Research: The Ethics and Aesthetics of Statistics*. London: Springer, pp.13-26.
- Lincoln, Y., Lynham, S., & Guba, E. (2018) 'Paradigmatic Controversies, Contradictions, and Emerging Confluences, Revisited', in N. Denzin & Y. Lincoln (eds.). *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research*. 5th edn. London: SAGE Publications, pp.108-150.
- McDermid, F. Peters, K. Jackson, D. and Daly, J. (2014) Conducting Qualitative Research in the Context of Pre-Existing Peer and Collegial Relationships, *Nurse Researcher*, 21 (5), pp.28–33. DOI:10.7748/nr.21.5.28.e1232
- Mercer, J. (2007) 'The challenges of insider research in educational institutions: wielding a double-edged sword and resolving delicate dilemmas', *Oxford Review of Education*, 33 (1) pp. 1-17.
- Mertens, D. (2015) *Research and evaluation in education and psychology: Integrating diversity with quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods*. 4th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Merriam, S. (1998) *Qualitative Research and Case Study Applications in Education*. NJ: Jossey-Bass Publishing.
- O'Connor, A., Carpenter, B. & Coughlan, B. (2018) 'An Exploration of Key Issues in the Debate Between Classic and Constructivist Grounded Theory', *The Grounded Theory Review*, 17 (1), pp.90-103
- Phillips, D.C & Burbules, N.C. (2000) *Postpositivism and Educational Research*. Lanham, MD: Rowman and Littlefield.
- Robson, C. (2002) *Real World Research*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.
- Schofield, J. (2009) 'Increasing the generalisability of qualitative research', in R. Gomm, M. Hammersley and P. Foster (Eds.) *Case Study Method*, (pp.69-97), SAGE Publications, <https://www-doi-org.dcu.idm.oclc.org/10.4135/9780857024367>
- Simons, H. (2009) *Case Study Research in Practice*. London: SAGE Publications.

Spencer, R., Pryce, J. M., & Walsh, J. (2014) 'Philosophical approaches to qualitative research' in Leavy, P. (ed.), *The Oxford handbook of qualitative research*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 81–98.

Stake, R. (1995) *The Art of Case Study Research*. London: SAGE Publications.

Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1994). 'Grounded theory methodology: An overview'. In N. Denzin & Y. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research* (pp. 273-285). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.

Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Sweetman, D., Badiee, M., & Creswell, J. (2010) 'Use of the Transformative Framework in Mixed Methods Studies', *Qualitative Inquiry*, 16 (6), pp.441-454. DOI: 10.1177/1077800410364610.

Teddle, C. & Tashakkori, A. (2012) Common "Core" Characteristics of Mixed Methods Research: A Review of Critical Issues and Call for Greater Convergence, in *American Behavioural Scientist*, 56 (6), pp.774-778. DOI: 10.1177/0002764211433795.

Tie, C.T., Birks, M., Francis, K. (2019) 'Grounded theory research: a design framework for novice researchers', *SAGE Open Medicine*, 7, pp.1–8. DOI: 10.1177/2050312118822927.

VanWynsberghe, R., & Khan, S. (2007). Redefining Case Study. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 80–94. <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940690700600208>

Walsh, I., Holton, J. A., Bailyn, L., Fernandez, W., Levina, N., & Glaser, B. (2015) 'What grounded theory is...A critically reflective conversation among scholars', *Organisational Research Methods*, 18 (4), pp.581-599. doi:10.1177/1094428114565028#

Yin, R.K., (1984) *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. LA: Sage Publications.

Yin, R.K., (2009) *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*, 4th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.